

Legal Considerations of Physicians Practicing Complementary and Alternative Medicine

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Abstract

There is a challenging legal landscape for medical doctors who, in addition to allopathic care, engage in complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) in the United States. While allopathic medicine and CAM have historically independently coexisted, the legal landscape has not adequately addressed the complex issues that physicians face when practicing CAM. Current law does not adequately shield providers from liability, limiting the future development of medicine's engagement with CAM as both relevant medical practices and legal frameworks develop. Considerations of scope of practice for allopathic and CAM providers is critical in assessing what is appropriate to consider medical care. Furthermore, lack of evidence-based practice associated with CAM, giving the field a conceptually experimental quality presents doctors both with opportunities and hindrances to appropriately engaging in CAM. Issues of informed consent and considerations of malpractice within the current American judicial system limit the way that physicians can legally approach CAM in their practice. By analyzing relevant legal precedent, this paper explores the regulation and the liability that allopathic physicians face when incorporating CAM in their clinical encounters.

Introduction

In the United States, allopathic medicine – “a system of medical practice that emphasizes diagnosing and treating disease and the use of conventional, evidence-based therapeutic measures[1] or Western Medicine – has been the foundation of much of modern healthcare.[2] This evidence-based practice is the backbone of the modern medical system and uses a disease-oriented approach to care. In the United States, different elements of medical care are highly regulated, such as medications and medical devices by the FDA,[3] the licensure of physicians by state medical boards,[4] and health-related regulations and laws at the state level.[5] The established supervising system has created an expansive structure for the regulation of what are considered ‘standard’ medical practices with clear frameworks of liability for practicing physicians guided by a variety of entities including national and state-level statutes and regulations, professional practice and clinical guidelines, and licensing boards.[6]

In parallel with common allopathic medical practice, there is a rich history of “complementary and alternative medicine” (CAM) in the United States. CAM, rooted in ancient tradition in contrast to the evidence-based approach of allopathic medicine, generally centers on a whole-body approach and encompasses practices such as acupuncture, herbal medicine, Tai Chi, Reiki, and Ayurveda. CAM practitioners are certified by their own overseeing bodies independent of the allopathic framework.[7] Issues arise in the increasingly murky arena when conventional providers integrate CAM practices into their medical practice. There has been a sharp delineation between Western medicine and CAM. However, CAM is often being used to supplement allopathic medicine and is increasingly embedded in the contemporary healthcare system.[8] When considering the complex issues that physicians face when employing complementary and alternative medicine, the law does not adequately shield providers from liability, limiting the future development of medicine’s engagement with CAM as both relevant medical practices and legal frameworks develop. This paper will explore the regulation of these encounters and the liability that allopathic physicians face when incorporating CAM in their clinical encounters.

Licensing of Complementary and Alternative Medicine in the United States

The use and practice of complementary and alternative medicine in the United States is broad and has many manifestations across disciplines. Independent of the conventional healthcare system, there is an extensive system of CAM providers engaging in a variety of practices such as hypnosis, acupuncture, naturopathy, and Qigong. These providers are licensed and certified by individual state licensing boards but are very restricted in terms of the scope of the care that they are allowed to provide. While allopathic physicians must also abide by state licensing statutes to provide medical care, the scope of practice provided by these statutes is much wider and less restrictive in terms of what medical advice can be given.[8] CAM providers are narrowly restricted in their scope of practice and limited in what “medicine” they can provide.

While licensure varies among states, general principles are consistent and limit CAM providers. *Dent v. West Virginia*, which addressed incorporating botanical approaches into medicine,[9] and *People v. Amber*, which considered the practice of acupuncture by a non-licensed medical provider,[10] have upheld the limitations on CAM providers to treat and diagnose beyond their limited scope of practice.[11] Furthermore, *State of Nebraska, Department of Health v John Hinze*, which concerned the practice of homeopathy and naturopathy without a medical license[12], *North Carolina v F. Belle Howard and J.C. Howard*, which addressed practicing naturopathy under the guise of being a doctor,[13], and *Roget I. Sabastier v State of Florida*, which considered the ramifications of practicing homeopathy with a medical license,[14] all limited the ability of non-allopathic practitioners to consider themselves “doctors;” this limitation was in the public’s best interest to preserve public trust in medical institutions.[15] As licensing boards and regulatory structures determine what care is appropriate and legal, one essential consideration of CAM in the United States is its integration with official allopathic medicine by licensed medical doctors. Questions about whether allopathic doctors must be licensed in CAM to provide,

endorse, or integrate CAM in their practice are critical. Aside from the need for a medical doctor to have CAM-specific licensure to provide such care, it is also necessary to determine whether a physician could uphold a sufficiently high standard of care when engaging in CAM. This standard of care must be consistent with what is expected of them by their training and overseeing medical bodies but also by the public's trust in medical care.

Provision of Complementary and Alternative Medicine

Despite the strict regulations on CAM providers' scope of practice, conventional medical doctors have broad latitude to provide care that they see as appropriate. Texas, for example, has a statute that allows medical doctors to provide CAM without obtaining the relevant CAM licensure, stating, a "licensed physician shall not be found guilty of unprofessional conduct or be found to have committed professional failure to practice medicine in an acceptable manner solely on the basis of employing a health care method of integrative or complementary medicine" provided that the risk of this approach is not greater than an established, evidence-based medical practice.[16] The legislature takes this approach by deeming CAM to be akin to implementing an unproven therapy such as new experimental treatment.[17] While "experimental" tends to imply new, this approach considers experimental treatment to be that which is non-standard due to still lacking a basis in evidence.

This approach is generally broader than other states' approaches, which tend to only require a physician to practice in congruence with what similar physicians would accept or provide as long as "conventional standards of care" have not been violated.[15] A lower standard of care exists for providers who solely work in CAM;[18] accordingly, this puts additional pressure on allopathic providers who employ CAM to demonstrate that their use of CAM is appropriate, safe, and efficacious. A failure to do so has the potential to cause harm, undermine public trust in medical institutions, and expose providers to medical malpractice cases. Furthermore, obtaining informed consent – i.e. ensuring that patients are aware of the risks of the medical intervention or the choice to not undertake a more conventional approach – is critically important to ensure that patients understand the nature of the care that they are receiving and how it may differ from the presumed allopathic, evidence-based treatment that they are expecting.[19]

Patients may seek CAM either from a provider of CAM or an allopathic provider. When a patient seeks out CAM from any provider, informed consent is less likely to be an issue. *Charell v Gonzalez*[20] determined that "patients may insulate their physicians from liability, either partially or wholly, when they assume treatment risks by agreeing to them in a voluntary or informed manner,"[21] including the provision of CAM. In these situations, the crux of the issue is whether it is appropriate for a Western-trained physician who is not trained in CAM to provide CAM; this is a potential issue of malpractice. To avoid malpractice, a physician's care must generally either reflect the standards of what a majority of peer physicians would do or provide care consistent with what a respected minority would do.[15] If there were a respected minority of practitioners who engage in a particular type of CAM, there is theoretically a scenario where doctors can safely and legally provide CAM, per the above standard for avoiding malpractice. This is analogous to the Texas approach that treats CAM as an experimental therapy with few experts in the field attempting new practices. Otherwise, legal precedent suggests that any allopathic doctor, regardless of their training in CAM, is engaging in malpractice through employing CAM in any professional setting that does not meet the criteria for experimental therapy.

However, there are considerable constraints in place before experimental therapy can be adopted. The leading indication for experimental therapy is a situation in which a patient has a condition for which there is currently no adequate other approach. Likewise, many patients become dissatisfied with allopathic medicine that they feel has failed their intractable chronic conditions.[3] Under these circumstances, it is conceivable that a patient could ask a provider for CAM and the doctor must determine whether they will be liable for malpractice if the care goes poorly, and the patient is harmed.

While doctors appear to have latitude to implement CAM – both by the approval of a respected minority and through freedoms to attempt experimental therapies – it still may be inadvisable for a provider to engage in CAM when requested. Although they do not need official licensure to practice CAM, it is reasonable to contend that a physician cannot adequately understand, prescribe, or provide CAM without licensure. Even if the type of CAM theoretically meets professional standards, the physician could potentially be liable if their delivery of the care is below standards given their lack of training. This issue is potentially sidestepped by doctors who obtain CAM licensure, but the mitigation of malpractice risk is theoretically only achieved by those doctors who only use CAM when requested in absence of a satisfactory allopathic alternative. This is clear in cases such as *Schneider v. Revici*, which established that, with an alternative allopathic approach available, an allopathic provider engages in malpractice by providing CAM even at the patient’s request.[20,22] Similarly, *Charell v Gonzalez*, determined that it is not acceptable for a provider to “deviat[e] from “acceptable medical standards”,”[20] which can be understood to include any form of CAM. However, this may not apply when there is not an established or acceptable medical approach to a conventional medical problem, especially when that non-established medical practice is sought by the patient.

The scope of when CAM is appropriate has been well defined for the patient who seeks an alternative to allopathic medicine. *Charell* suggests that physicians who provide CAM have engaged in malpractice, even when the CAM is sought out by the patient. Although *Charell* indicates that a patient could theoretically insulate their provider from liability by requesting CAM, the physician’s requirement not to deviate from acceptable medical standards to avoid malpractice takes priority. *Schneider* limits CAM malpractice to the provision of CAM when an adequate allopathic alternative exists. Critically, however, both cases involved a patient who sought out CAM from their doctor. Based on current precedent, it seems that the most difficult legal cases involving CAM would be when a non-CAM-trained doctor wants to provide CAM – in the absence of an appropriate alternative allopathic treatment - to a patient who has not actively sought it. When patients have conditions for which allopathic medicine doesn’t have a satisfactory intervention, physicians are in uncharted medical territory. Experimental therapies, which are typically grounded in evidence-based, allopathic interventions, are often the first approach. However, a CAM approach could also be considered experimental under the present circumstances. Accordingly, it would not deviate from acceptable practice when provided by an appropriately trained physician. This appears to create a scenario under which an allopathic physician could appropriately provide CAM to a patient.

However, in addition to the malpractice issues discussed above, the matter of informed consent is amplified in this scenario. A doctor suggesting a CAM approach to a CAM-naïve patient is likely unable to rely on the exception carved out by *Charell*: release of the doctor from liability by a patient who assumes all risk on behalf of the physician. A physician requiring a patient to assume all risk for an experimental treatment, even in the face of no alternative treatment modality, seems manipulative by the physician and puts undue pressure on the patient. It seems unlikely that a patient could appropriately and independently consent to an experimental treatment under this condition.

The suggestion of a complementary or alternative medical practice never falls within a physician’s duty of care, but this does not necessarily prohibit a physician from acknowledging CAM.[23] A well-studied, safe, effective alternative medical practice in which the provider is trained, delivered in the absence of acceptable other established therapies, is the narrow window in which an allopathic provider may be able to practice CAM without fear of liability. This is a new area as CAM becomes more mainstream and researched; unsurprisingly, the law has not yet addressed these emerging developments.

Consequences of the Legal Landscape for Complementary and Alternative Medicine

The legal landscape surrounding CAM has created an environment that inhibits the use of CAM in contemporary medicine. The most risk-averse position for physicians to take is never to engage with CAM. This approach eliminates the potential for CAM-related malpractice. However, as CAM practices become more researched and mainstream, there is an increasing legitimacy for physicians (who have been licensed in CAM) to provide this type of care for intractable medical conditions.

Nevertheless, fear of malpractice seems to be a potent deterrent for doctors considering adopting CAM or engaging with CAM-oriented clinical research. The current environment creates a Catch-22 for CAM: CAM practice isn't protected or mainstream so doctors are disincentivized to engage with or research it out of fear of liability; accordingly, because CAM is not researched and protected, it cannot become established and considered an acceptable medical practice. Under the current legal landscape, changes that increase the research around or provision of CAM in the United States are not to be expected. Under these conditions, the author would discourage any provider from engaging in CAM for risk of malpractice cases and violations of informed consent. However, the status quo does not make the extensive history of CAM and patient interest in CAM disappear.

Elsewhere in the world, complementary and alternative medical practice and research is embedded into the healthcare system and legislation. India has a robust history of supporting CAM, both by legally recognizing it as legitimate and by licensing CAM providers at the same level as allopathic doctors.[24] While a seismic shift in the landscape of CAM in the United States – akin to how India views CAM – is not necessarily indicated, the presence of another established system suggests that the United States' approach to CAM may be too restrictive. The current regulatory environment and liability for physicians stifles much consideration of CAM and will continue to do so moving forward. While it is important to preserve the trust in the healthcare system, which in part derives from an established, evidence-based foundation, there are opportunities for the law to allow physicians to engage in CAM in wider circumstances, provided that they are doing so with appropriately extensive training and that their practice is not at the expense of established allopathic medicine.

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